

Biamperometric Determination of Copper, Lead, Manganese(II), Cobalt and Nickel with Two Polarised Electrodes

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Biamperometric technique using two stationary platinum electrodes at Constant applied voltage has been used to estimate copper, lead, manganese (II) cobalt and nickel at low concentrations. The pH at which elements were estimated was between 2.5 to 3.5. The percentage error was observed within $\pm 1.0\%$.

VARIOUS methods¹⁻³² for the determination of copper, lead, manganese (ii), cobalt and nickel have been developed. Usatenko and Uvarova³³ determined copper amperometrically with Sodium pentamethylene dithiocarbamate using lead ions as indicator. Singh and Varma³⁴ determined lead amperometrically with fluoride using two identical polarised platinum electrodes at constant applied voltage in the presence of small amounts of ferric chloride as an indicator. Rao and Rao³⁵ titrated manganese (ii) with standard potassium dichromate solution in strong phosphoric acid medium using a potentiometric end point. Pribil and Svestka³⁶ estimated cobalt with potassium dichromate solution in acid medium. Singh and Varma³⁷ determined nickel (ii) amperometrically by iodine solution in the presence of alcoholic dimethylglyoxime solution in ammoniacal medium. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to develop a biamperometric technique using two platinum electrodes at constant voltage for a rapid and direct determination of copper, lead, manganese (ii), cobalt and nickel at low concentrations.

Experimental

Copper, lead, manganese (ii), cobalt and nickel salts used were of B. D. H. or Merck's extrapure quality. The respective sulphates and nitrates of copper, manganese(ii), cobalt, nickel and lead were dissolved separately in conductivity water and their content was estimated complexometrically with standard EDTA solution using indicator method³⁸. Standard solution 0.05M of EDTA was prepared and standardized using standard method³⁹. The desired concentrations of the solutions were obtained by appropriate dilutions. Experimental set up is similar to that as described by stone and scholten³⁹.

End points were determined graphically by the usual plot of the current against volume of the titrant added. A typical titration curve is shown in Figure 1. Results of the investigations are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The method described is based on electro-oxidation of free EDTA on a platinum anode in the pH range

2.5 to 3.5. On addition of EDTA solution metal chelates are formed and no electro-oxidation of EDTA occurs. If a potential of the order of 1.1 volts is applied to two platinum electrodes the residual current is registered upto the equivalence point but the current rises abruptly due to the oxidation of EDTA after the equivalence point. The titration curve has usually-shape (reverse L type). The reaction involved in the present titration is stoichiometric and quantitative with a sharp break at 1 : 1 ratio between elements and EDTA ions. The results obtained were within 1.0% error.

Fig. 1. Determination of 0.1270 mg copper present in solution.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF COPPER, LEAD, MANGANESE(II), COBALT AND NICKEL.

S. No.	Amount in mg Taken	Found	Experimental Average	Error % Maximum
(Copper)				
1.	1.2708	1.2689	+0.53	+1.75
2.	0.6355	0.6361	+0.33	+2.0
3.	0.3177	0.3165	-1.0	-2.5
4.	0.1588	0.1594	+0.67	+1.5
5.	0.1270	0.1270	-0.16	-1.0
(Lead)				
6.	2.0719	2.0678	+0.73	+2.5
7.	1.5538	1.5579	+0.24	+1.35
8.	1.0359	1.0380	-0.54	-1.50
9.	0.5179	0.5162	+0.44	+1.75
10.	0.4144	0.4140	-0.67	-1.80
(Manganese II)				
11.	0.5493	0.5503	-0.47	-1.7
12.	0.4119	0.4102	-0.35	-1.65
13.	0.2746	0.2750	+0.87	+2.0
14.	0.1373	0.1380	+0.63	+1.85
15.	0.0589	0.0587	-0.67	-2.0
(Cobalt)				
16.	0.5893	0.6887	+0.43	+1.75
17.	0.2946	0.2950	-0.33	-1.25
18.	0.1473	0.1587	+0.53	+1.55
19.	0.1178	0.1170	+1.12	+2.50
20.	0.0589	0.0587	-0.67	-2.0
(Nickel)				
21.	0.5871	0.5856	+0.47	+1.75
22.	0.2935	0.2940	-0.16	-1.0
23.	0.1467	0.1475	+0.45	+1.35
24.	0.0587	0.0586	-0.34	-1.5

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